

How does high school extracurricular participation predict bachelor's degree attainment?

It's complicated

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Abstract

This study answered novel questions about the connection between high school extracurricular dosage (number of activities and participation duration) and the attainment of a bachelor's degree. Using data from the Common Application and the National Student Clearinghouse ($N = 311,308$), we found that greater extracurricular participation positively predicted bachelor's degree attainment. However, among students who ultimately earned a bachelor's degree, participating in more than a moderate number of high school activities (3 or 4) predicted decreasing odds of earning a bachelor's degree *on time* (within 4 years). This effect intensified as participation duration increased, such that students who participated in the greatest number of high school activities for the most years were the most likely to delay college graduation.

College credentials are a critical determinant of success in the 21st century economy. Accordingly, the number of enrolled postsecondary students in the U.S. has risen dramatically over the last half century, from 3.6 million in 1959 (Haskins, Holzer, & Lerman, 2009) to 16.8 million in 2017 (McFarland et al., 2019). Growth in college enrollment has outpaced growth in college completion, however. Only 59% of youth who enroll in a four-year college earn a bachelor's degree within six years (40%; Snyder, de Brey, & Dillow, 2018). Leaving college without a degree places young adults at a distinct disadvantage. On average, those who enroll but do not complete college earn only two-thirds of the income earned by four-year graduates, and are more likely to be unemployed (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2019).

Identifying the predictors of bachelor's degree completion is a key first step toward boosting the percentage of students who earn a four-year degree. Yet, research on this critical task has fallen short. Taken together, high school GPA, ACT/SAT scores, and other common predictors of college success (e.g., gender, race/ethnicity, financial aid) explain only 14% to 20% of the variance in rates of bachelor's degree attainment (Attewell, Heil, & Reisel, 2011). Thus, in the present study, we look to participation in extracurricular activities during high school (e.g., school clubs, student government, sports, music lessons, community service) to account for previously unexplained variance in the attainment of a bachelor's degree.

The effects of adolescent extracurricular participation on the attainment of a four-year degree are not yet well understood, but extracurricular participation has been linked to a multitude of other positive academic outcomes, including better grades, higher test scores, higher educational expectations, better classroom behavior, better attitudes toward school, and even higher rates of college enrollment (see Feldman & Matjasko, 2005; Farb & Matjasko, 2012 for reviews). Below, we argue that theory developed to explain links between extracurricular

participation and these academic outcomes may also support links between extracurricular participation and the attainment of a bachelor's degree. Additionally, building on the extracurricular dosage literature, we consider whether spending more time in extracurricular activities may increase students' odds of earning a bachelor's degree, and whether the amount of time spent in extracurricular activities has any bearing on the amount of time it takes students to complete a bachelor's degree.

Extracurricular participation and academic outcomes

Extracurricular activities take many forms. They cover a variety of content areas and may be sponsored by schools (e.g., school sports teams, marching band, debate teams, science clubs, student government) or by groups or individuals within the community (e.g., community sports leagues, church youth groups, music lessons). Yet they all have the following characteristics in common: They are regularly scheduled, adult-supervised, structured out-of-school-time activities that focus on developing skills and/or achieving goals (Mahoney, Larson, Eccles, & Lord, 2005).

Many of the hypothesized mechanisms linking extracurricular participation and developmental success – including academic achievement – have been summarized and synthesized in Lerner's (2005) theory of positive youth development. Lerner (2005) argues that the positive outcomes associated with organized youth activities derive from some combination of relationships with supportive adults, skill-building activities, and the provision of opportunities for leadership and community engagement. Other scholars have made similar arguments (e.g., Broh, 2002; Eccles & Gootman, 2002; Larson, Walker, & Pearce, 2005; Roth and Brooks-Gunn, 2003). Beyond providing warmth and security (Eccles & Gootman, 2002), relationships with supportive adults can serve both as social ties that transmit educational values and resources and as social controls that encourage adherence to academic conventions and

norms (Broh, 2002). Skill-building activities – whether in the context of sports, the arts, academics, or other activities – can provide opportunities for the development of non-cognitive skills such as perseverance (Duckworth, 2016) and self-confidence (Broh, 2002) that carry over into educational pursuits. Community engagement may further strengthen social ties and social controls, while opportunities for leadership and (supervised) student-directed activities may facilitate the development of academically relevant non-cognitive skills like initiative (Larson, 2000; Larson et al., 2005).

These mechanisms, and their hypothesized benefits, are applicable across a wide variety of extracurricular activities. Although some studies find differences in the academic effects of participation in school- versus community-sponsored activities, the direction of differences varies from study to study and research does not consistently suggest that sponsorship of one kind is better than the other (see Brown & Evans, 2002; Chambers & Schreiber, 2004; Gardner, Roth, & Brooks-Gunn, 2008; Marsh & Kleitman, 2002; Rose-Krasnor, Busseri, Willoughby, & Chalmers, 2006). Similarly, the specific types of activities that youth participate in – for example, music versus academic clubs, or theater versus student government – generally matter less than *whether* or not youth participate (see Feldman & Matjasko, 2005; Farb & Matjasko, 2012). In fact, sports are the only consistent exception in an otherwise positive pattern of associations between participation in a wide variety of extracurricular activities and outcomes across many developmental domains. Athletes are more likely than non-athletes to engage in a number of adolescent and young adult problem behaviors (e.g., substance use, delinquency; Darling, Caldwell, & Smith, 2005; Denault, Poulin, & Pederson, 2009; Fauth, Roth, & Brooks-Gunn, 2007; Fredricks & Eccles, 2005; 2008; Hartmann & Massoglia, 2007; Hoffmann, 2006;

Kreager, 2007; McHale et al., 2005); nonetheless, sports participation still tends to predict academic success (Feldman & Matjasko, 2005; Farb & Matjasko, 2012).

Yet, a notable gap remains in our knowledge of extracurricular participation and academic success. College enrollment is among the academic outcomes that have been linked with high school extracurricular participation (e.g., Eccles & Barber, 1999; Eccles, Barber, Stone, & Hunt, 2003; Gardner et al., 2008; Mahoney et al., 2003; Marsh & Kleitman, 2003; Stevenson, 2010; Zaff, Moore, Papillo, & Williams, 2003), and studies further suggest that high school extracurricular participation predicts more years of postsecondary enrollment (Barron, Ewing, & Waddell, 2000; Eccles et al., 2003, Mahoney et al., 2003; Marsh & Kleitman, 2003). However, surprisingly few studies have considered the possibility that the effects of high school extracurricular participation may extend beyond college enrollment to earning a bachelor's degree *per se*. This distinction is critical given both overall low national rates of completion (Snyder, de Brey, & Dillow, 2018) and the superior long-term economic performance of students who complete a four-year degree program relative to those who enroll in such programs without completing them (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2019).

Further, there is no reason to expect the academic benefits of extracurricular participation to end with college enrollment. The mechanisms invoked above can easily be extended to explain why participation in high school extracurricular activities may increase the odds of earning a bachelor's degree. Indeed, researchers who have examined relations between adolescent extracurricular participation and number of years of postsecondary enrollment have often extrapolated from theory that explains academic outcomes in adolescence (Eccles et al., 2003, Mahoney et al., 2003; Marsh & Kleitman, 2003). If the academic values and non-cognitive skills developed through extracurricular participation in high school persist into young

adulthood, then youth who participate in extracurricular activities in high school should be more likely than non-participants to earn a four-year degree. Strong educational values and qualities and skills such as perseverance, planning, and initiative should equip students with the motivation and resources necessary to identify a roadmap to college graduation, monitor progress, and surmount obstacles that may arise along the way.

The existing evidence, while scant, is generally consistent with this perspective. The first study to focus explicitly on the connection between extracurricular activities and college persistence (i.e., continued enrollment through senior year) was conducted over 30 years ago. In this investigation, Willingham (1985) followed 4,800 high school seniors and found that sustained (i.e., multi-year) participation and accomplishments in high school extracurricular activities were among the best measured predictors of both persistent college enrollment through senior year and college honors and accomplishments. This analysis did not track actual degree completion, however. Only four studies have examined associations between extracurricular participation and the attainment of a four-year degree, and three of these studies focused narrowly on the influence of sports. All three sports studies found positive associations between high school sports participation and the attainment of a bachelor's degree (Eide & Ronan, 2001; Spreitzer, 1994; Troutman & Dufur, 2007). One of these studies, however, observed the benefits of sports only among White girls; positive effects did not extend to boys, African American girls, or Latinas (Eide & Ronan, 2001). The fourth study cast a broader net, considering all types of extracurricular activities, and found that more consistent, intensive participation in either school- or community-sponsored extracurricular activities during high school predicted greater odds of earning a bachelor's degree within eight years of finishing high school (Gardner, Roth, & Brooks-Gunn, 2008). Because this fourth study is the only study that has considered the effects

of activities other than sports on college completion, more research examining the predictive power of participation in an array of activity types is needed.

How much extracurricular participation is best?

An additional pertinent question pertains to the level of extracurricular participation that best predicts college graduation. Typically, studies find that more, versus less, participation in extracurricular activities predicts better outcomes across multiple developmental domains, no matter how dosage is measured (e.g., number of activities, length or frequency of participation; see Busseri, Rose-Krasnor, Willoughby, & Chalmers, 2006; Darling, 2005; Darling, Caldwell, & Smith, 2005; Gardner et al., 2008; Mahoney, Cairns, & Farmer, 2003; Rose-Krasnor, Busseri, Willoughby, & Chalmers, 2006; Zaff et al., 2003). Interpreted through the lens of positive youth development theory (Lerner, 2005), the heightened benefits of longer-term participation in more extracurricular activities may stem from stronger relationships with a greater number of supportive adults, more opportunities for skill-building activities, and more opportunities for community engagement and leadership. In other words, if some exposure to these developmental supports and opportunities is beneficial, more exposure is even better.

Notably, this perspective runs counter to two schools of thought – the zero-sum perspective and the overscheduling hypothesis – that warn against the perils of extracurricular over-involvement. The zero-sum argument suggests that extracurricular activities compete with and detract from academic work (see Marsh & Kleitman, 2002), while the overscheduling hypothesis suggests that excessive involvement in extracurricular activities is a stressor that adversely impacts well-being (see Mahoney et al., 2006). That said, most studies measuring high school academic outcomes and college enrollment do not support zero-sum or overscheduling hypotheses (Busseri et al., 2006; Darling, 2005; Darling et al., 2005; Gardner et al., 2008;

Mahoney et al., 2003; Rose-Krasnor et al., 2006; Zaff et al., 2003). Accordingly, and for all the reasons discussed above, we expect that students who are more, versus, less highly involved in extracurricular activities in high school will ultimately earn bachelor's degrees at higher rates (Gardner et al., 2008; Troutman & Dufur, 2007).

We leave room, however, for the possibility that high levels of extracurricular involvement may slow the attainment of a bachelor's degree. Past behavior is a good predictor of future behavior, and if students who are very involved in extracurricular activities in high school continue to invest large amounts of time in extracurricular activities during college, they may find it difficult to complete the requirements for a bachelor's degree within four years. Although high levels of extracurricular involvement may not compromise performance in college classes (just as high levels of extracurricular involvement do not appear to compromise high school academic performance), heavy extracurricular loads in college could conceivably lead to reduced course-taking and a longer path to graduation. This is a novel line of inquiry; research has not explored the influence of extracurricular dosage on the timing of college graduation, let alone on intermediate outcomes like course-taking. Further, because most high school students follow a relatively prescribed curriculum and path to graduation, delayed graduation is an outcome with no real parallel in the high school literature. Thus, while intuitive, this hypothesis is necessarily speculative.

At first blush, hypotheses linking high levels of extracurricular involvement and delayed college graduation may appear to invoke a zero-sum game, wherein extracurricular activities and academics are competitors, and one can win only if the other loses. But that is only the case if "winning" the game is defined as taking no more than four years to earn a bachelor's degree. It is not clear, however, that delays in college graduation should necessarily and always be

considered disadvantageous. Educators, advocates, and the general public are rightfully concerned about the short-term economic consequences of a delayed path to a four-year degree; students who do not earn a bachelor's degree within four years face higher educational costs and lost wage-earning opportunities on the order of tens of thousands of dollars (Complete College America, 2014). However, it is possible, and even plausible, that not all delayed paths to a bachelor's degree are created equal. Delays in degree attainment caused by financial difficulty, remedial coursework, and other academic problems may indeed have a net negative impact on a student's economic future and general well-being. Delays in degree attainment caused by participation in enriching activities that provide opportunities for the development of human and social capital, on the other hand, may have altogether different consequences. The long-term economic, social, and emotional benefits of such opportunities may outweigh any financial consequences associated with higher educational costs and lost wage-earning opportunities that occur in the short-term. This is a prospect that research has not yet explored. Thus, while we consider the possibility that high levels of extracurricular involvement may lengthen the path to a bachelor's degree, we remain agnostic about whether this should be cause for concern.

The Present Study

Drawing on the rationale outlined above, we consider whether two dimensions of high school extracurricular participation – the number of activities in which students participate and activity duration (i.e., number of years in each activity) – predict the on-time and delayed attainment of a bachelor's degree (within four and six years of college enrollment, respectively). We examine the linear, curvilinear, additive, and multiplicative effects of these two dimensions of extracurricular participation on college outcomes. Further, we test whether these dimensions of high school extracurricular participation predict plans to continue participating in

extracurricular activities during college, and whether these plans, in turn, predict the attainment of a bachelor's degree.

We note an important limitation at the outset, however. We rely on observational rather than experimental data, and associations documented in our analyses therefore reflect selection bias to an unknown degree. This is a nearly universal shortcoming in the extracurricular literature (see Feldman & Matjasko, 2012 and Shulruf, 2010 for discussion and review). Random assignment is the gold standard for eliminating selection bias and demonstrating causality, but the assurance of a "pure" control group (i.e., abstinence from all organized activities) makes experimental research virtually impossible in the extracurricular arena. Statistical approaches such as propensity score modeling and instrumental variable analyses approximate experimental designs in observational data, and the few studies that have used these techniques studies (e.g., Connor & Jose, 2012; Edie & Ronan, 2007; Glanville, 1999; Lipscomb, 2007; Stevenson, 2010) suggest that removing selection bias decreases, but does not eliminate, the positive effects of extracurricular participation. Our data were not well-suited for these methods, however (see more in the Discussion section). Thus, we minimize selection bias by including controls in conventional regression models for variables that may impact both selection into extracurricular activities and college outcomes. Because students with socioeconomic advantages and stronger academic performance are both more likely to select into extracurricular activities (Feldman & Matjasko, 2005) and more likely to graduate from college (Attewell et al., 2011), our models of college graduation control for admission test scores and a variety of sociodemographic characteristics.

We cannot, however, control for the impact of unknown and/or unmeasured selection factors. Selection into multiple years of extracurricular activities could, for example, reflect

unmeasured characteristics such as perseverance that may also increase the probability of college graduation, thereby upwardly biasing regression estimates. (See Duckworth, 2016 for a discussion of links between extracurricular participation, perseverance, and college success.) Little research has considered the impact of personality on selection into extracurricular activities (see Glanville, 1999 for one exception); thus, this statement is necessarily conjecture, offered only as illustrative possibility. The point is simply that, because we cannot account for all such selection factors, we cannot draw conclusions about the causal effects of extracurricular participation on whether and when students will graduate from college with a bachelor's degree. What we can do, however, is determine whether and to what extent high school extracurricular participation *predicts* this critically important accomplishment.

Method

All research activities described below were approved by our Institutional Review Board.

Sample

Our sample was drawn from the population of students who completed the Common Application (Common App) in the 2008/2009 academic year for college admission during the 2009/2010 academic year ($N = 413,675$). The Common App is an online, universal college application used by roughly 800 colleges and universities (www.commonapp.org). Students typically complete the application in the fall of their senior year of high school, though submission dates vary depending on the application deadlines of the colleges that students apply to (www.princetonreview.com/college-advice/common-application). From this population, we selected students who had not enrolled in a postsecondary institution prior to 2008 ($N = 311,308$). This inclusion criterion ensured the accuracy of records reflecting time to degree attainment. We then obtained matched college enrollment and degree attainment data from the

2015 National Student Clearinghouse (NSC) database (www.studentclearinghouse.org). All data processing and matching was done by a third party, who provided us with a de-identified dataset.

Just over half the sample (55%) was female. Fifty-one percent of the sample identified themselves as White, 10% identified as Asian, 6% identified as African American, 6% identified as Latino, 8% identified as a member of another race/ethnic group or multiple race/ethnic groups, and 18% did not endorse any race/ethnic category. The majority of students spoke English as a first language (88%) and had married parents (78%). Nearly half of students (49%) had two parents with a college degree, 24% had one parent with a college degree, and 26% reported that neither of their parents had a college degree. Fifty-one percent of students attended a non-Title I public high school, 16% attended a Title I public high school, 33% attended a private high school, and less than 1% of students were homeschooled.

Measures

Descriptive statistics for all measures are provided in Table 1.

Bachelor's degree attainment. Using data from the NSC, we constructed three binary measures of college graduation: (1) on-time bachelor's attainment versus no bachelor's (1 = earned bachelor's within four years; 0 = 2015 NSC data indicates no bachelor's obtained); (2) late bachelor's attainment versus no bachelor's (1 = earned a bachelor's in more than four years but within six years; 0 = 2015 NSC data indicates no bachelor's obtained); and (3) on-time bachelor's versus late bachelor's attainment (1 = earned a bachelor's within four years; 0 = earned a bachelor's in more than four years but within six years).

High school extracurricular activities. In completing the Common App, students responded to the following open-ended prompt: "Please list your principal extracurricular, community, volunteer, and family activities and hobbies in order of their interest to you."

Students were allowed to enter up to seven activities. The vast majority (over 94%) of activities reported were traditional extracurricular activities (i.e., organized sports, music lessons, school clubs). Students also reported the number of years that they participated in each activity. From these data, we computed both the number of activities in which students participated and activity duration (i.e., average number of years per activity).

Number of planned college activities. Students indicated whether they planned to continue each of their reported extracurricular activities during college. From these data, we computed the number of activities that students planned to continue during college.

Control variables. College attainment is correlated with a number of demographic characteristics and indicators of socioeconomic status (Attewell et al., 2011) that are also correlated with extracurricular participation (Feldman & Matjasko, 2005). Thus, all models controlled for gender, race/ethnicity (five dummy codes for African American, Latino, Asian, other, and no race/ethnicity reported versus White), parents' marital status (1 = *married*, 0 = *not married*), parent education (two dummy codes for one or two versus zero parents with a college degree), native language (1 = *English is first language*, 0 = *English is not first language*), and type of high school (three dummy codes for Title I public high school, private school, and homeschool versus non-Title I public high school).

Second, we controlled for the proportion of reported activities that were sports. As previously noted, sports participation has been linked with negative behavioral outcomes like substance use that may impede college progress. Further, a prior study failed to find uniformly positive associations between high school sports participation and college graduation (Eide & Ronan, 2007). Because both number of extracurricular activities and duration were significantly associated with the number of high school sports that students participated in ($r = .21, p < .001$

and $r = .05$, $p < .001$, respectively), this control was necessary to prevent conflating high levels of overall extracurricular involvement with high levels of sports involvement.

Third, because academic performance predicts both selection into extracurricular activities (Feldman & Matjasko, 2005) and college graduation (Attewell et al., 2011), we controlled for admissions test scores. Over half (55%) of our sample only took the SAT, 14% only took the ACT, and 25% took both tests. Composite SAT scores ranged from 600 to 2400 ($M = 1805.7$, $SD = 268.2$), and composite ACT scores ranged from 1 to 36 ($M = 27.1$, $SD = 4.4$). To construct a single test score composite, we converted ACT scores to SAT scores using publicly available guidelines (ACT, 2013). For students who took both tests, we selected the higher score.

Finally, to account for correlations between high levels of extracurricular involvement and the quality of colleges attended, we controlled for institutional rates of four-year bachelor's degree completion. From public data (National Center for Education Statistics, 2018), we obtained rates of four-year bachelor's attainment for the postsecondary institution that each student was attending three years after application in 2012. (If a student was not attending college three years after application due to early graduation or drop-out, we used institutional degree attainment rates from the last school that they attended.) We opted not to use institutional degree attainment rates collected in 2013 – four years after application – because these institutional rates would be based, in part, on degree attainment among our sample members (many of whom earned bachelor's degrees in 2013).

Analytic plan

Missing data. Approximately 6%, 7%, and 12% of students were missing data on admission tests, high school type, and institutional rates of bachelor's degree attainment,

respectively. There were no other missing data. Missing data were multiply imputed in Stata 14.2 (StataCorp, 2015) using the “mi ice” program. We created 25 imputed datasets.

Main analysis. First, using logistic regression models, we regressed our three college outcomes (on-time versus no bachelor's, late versus no bachelor's, and on-time versus late bachelor's) on all above-described controls and both measures of high school extracurricular participation. Quadratic terms for number of extracurricular activities and participation duration were tested and retained if they were significant predictors of college outcomes. We also included multiplicative terms to test for interactions between these two extracurricular measures. We retained statistically significant interactions in final models and conducted follow-up tests to unpack these interactions using procedures outlined by Aiken and West (1991).¹

Next, we regressed number of planned college activities on our measures of high school extracurricular participation, along with all the aforementioned controls. Poisson models were used because our outcome – number of planned number of college activities – is a count variable. Tests for quadratic terms and interactions were performed as described above. Finally, we regressed our three college outcomes on linear and quadratic terms for number of planned college activities and all control variables.

Given the large size of our sample, we used a two-tailed $p < .01$ rather than $p < .05$ as our criterion for statistical significance.²

Results

Effects of high school extracurriculars on on-time bachelor's versus no bachelor's degree

We found a significant interaction between number of activities squared and activity duration (see Table 2 and Figure 1, left panel). To unpack this interaction and facilitate interpretation, we computed coefficients and conducted significance tests for the linear and

quadratic effects of number of high school activities at each of the four levels of extracurricular duration (1, 2, 3, and 4 years per activity; see Aiken & West, 1991). These tests revealed significant positive linear associations between number of activities and on-time bachelor's attainment across all four levels of duration (see Table 3). Small negative quadratic effects across all but the lowest duration level revealed diminishing positive returns as the number of activities approached seven. As is evident in Figure 1 (left panel), participating in more activities generally predicted greater odds of a four-year bachelor's (versus no bachelor's) across all duration levels, and duration amplified the positive effects of number of activities. Overlapping 99% prediction intervals among youth at adjacent duration levels, however, suggest that differences as a function of duration may only be observed between youth who participated in each activity for one versus three or four years, and between youth who participated for two versus four years.

Effects of high school extracurriculars on late bachelor's versus no bachelor's degree

We found a significant two-way interaction between number of activities and duration squared (see Table 2 and Figure 1 – middle panel). Number of activities was positively associated with late bachelor's attainment (versus no bachelor's) across all duration levels (see Table 3). This positive association was stronger among students who participated in each activity for two or more years versus one year. Participation in activities for more than two years, however, had little additional impact on the relationship between number of activities and late bachelor's attainment. The non-linear (i.e., quadratic) moderating effect of duration in this model is clearly illustrated by the unevenly spaced trend lines in the middle panel of Figure 1.

Effects of high school extracurriculars on on-time bachelor's versus late bachelor's degree

We found a significant interaction between number of activities squared and duration (see Table 2 and Figure 1). In follow-up analyses, we computed linear and quadratic coefficients for

number of activities at each level of duration (see Table 3). Across duration levels, we found a null to slightly positive association between number of activities and on-time bachelor's attainment (versus late graduation) for up to three or four activities, after which participating in more activities predicted decreasing odds of earning a bachelor's degree on time. This effect intensified as duration increased, such that students who participated in the greatest number of activities for the most years were the least likely to earn a bachelor's on time (versus late).

Effects of high school extracurricular participation on number of planned college activities

We found a significant interaction between number of activities squared and duration squared (see Table 2) in models predicting number of planned college activities. Follow-up analyses (see Table 4) indicated that greater duration – particularly participation for three or four years – amplified the largely positive effect of number of high school activities on number of planned college activities (see Figure 2). Thus, students who participated in more activities over more years during high school planned on engaging in more extracurricular activities in college.

Effects of number of planned college activities on bachelor's degree attainment

Number of planned college activities had a small negative association with on-time bachelor's attainment versus no bachelor's, and a small positive association with the late attainment versus no bachelor's (see Table 5). When we limited the sample to students who ultimately earned a bachelor's degree (on-time or late), we found a negative association between number of planned activities and on-time (versus late) degree attainment. Due to a significant curvilinear effect, however, this negative association began to plateau as the number of planned activities approached seven (see Table 5 and Figure 3).

Discussion

Research has identified positive associations between the amount of time that students

devote to extracurricular activities and a wide variety of academic outcomes (Busseri et al., 2006; Darling, 2005; Darling et al., 2005; Gardner et al., 2008; Mahoney et al., 2003; Rose-Krasnor et al., 2006; Zaff et al., 2003). Our findings on college attainment are consistent with and also extend the findings of these studies. We found that students who participated in more extracurricular activities for more years during high school were more likely to earn a bachelor's degree – in four or six years – than were students who participated in fewer high school activities for fewer years. These findings are compatible with theoretical work, reviewed above, which suggests that extracurricular activities may provide unique opportunities for the development of academic values, resources, and educationally relevant non-cognitive characteristics such as self-confidence, perseverance, and initiative. These results alone enhance a literature that has considered a wide variety of academic outcomes and even college enrollment, but that has revealed relatively little about the association between high school extracurricular participation and the attainment of a four-year college degree (see Eide & Ronan, 2001; Gardner et al., 2008; Troutman & Dufur, 2007 for exceptions). Given the economic importance of earning a bachelor's degree, this study fills a critical gap in the extracurricular literature.

Our findings do more, however, than add an important outcome to an already large literature on the positive academic outcomes associated with high school extracurricular participation. Results from the present study contribute a more nuanced perspective to this body of work. We found that although investing more time in more extracurricular activities during high school increased the odds of earning a bachelor's degree, high levels of extracurricular involvement predicted a longer path to a degree. Specifically, when we restricted our sample to students who ultimately earned a bachelor's degree during our study period, we found that the odds of earning a bachelor's degree within four years – versus six years – were lowest among

students who reported the highest levels of extracurricular participation during high school (i.e., the greatest number of activities for the most years).

Our analyses of plans for college activities provide a plausible explanatory mechanism for this finding. Students who were the most involved in high school extracurricular activities – across both dimensions of participation – planned to continue participating in the greatest number of activities in college. Further, we found that more planned college activities predicted lower odds of on-time degree attainment. Though speculative, one reasonable hypothesis is that students who participate in more activities in college may take fewer credit hours each semester to allow time for these activities without compromising their academic performance. This strategy may, in turn, lengthen the time to graduation. We were unable to test this mechanism because our measures captured only the number of activities in which students *planned* to participate during college; we did not have a measure of the *actual* number of activities that students participated in during college. Moreover, we lacked the measures of students' decision-making about college course-taking, actual course-taking, and course performance that would be needed to fully test this mediational pathway. Our findings are therefore merely suggestive. Future research should collect the data necessary to test this mechanism.

Future research should also use causal methods that overcome selection bias. As we noted in the Introduction, our analyses cannot rule out the possibility that relations between extracurricular participation, college completion, and time to completion are driven by unmeasured third variables. In the absence of causal methods, our findings *cannot* and *should not* be used to make prescriptive recommendations regarding the number of activities that youth should take on during high school, or the number of years that they should stick with these activities. The experimental research necessary to prove causality is a near practical impossibility

in the field of extracurricular activities, and our data were not well-suited to statistical techniques for observational data that approximate experimental designs. Propensity score matching, which balances “treated” and “untreated” cases on measured covariates, was not possible because we did not have a single discrete “treatment.” Rather, our analyses revealed a complex interaction between two dosage variables – number of extracurricular activities and years of participation. Further, propensity score matching, like traditional regression, does not eliminate bias attributed to unmeasured selection factors (Steiner & Kim, 2016), thereby precluding strong causal inferences.

Instrumental variable analysis – a stronger causal method for observational data – improves on this shortcoming. In this type of analysis, an “instrument” (a variable that predicts the independent variable, but that has no impact on the dependent variable except through its impact on the independent variable) is used to isolate the variability in the independent variable that is free of unmeasured confounds. This variability is then used to estimate the causal influence of the independent variable (see Baiocchi, Cheng, & Small, 2014). The nature of our dataset rendered this approach impossible. Data in the Common App are collected for the purpose of identifying students who are likely to succeed in college. Thus, we lacked an instrumental variable that predicted selection into extracurricular activities without directly predicting college graduation. Difficulty finding an instrument may not be unique to our study. Instruments that predict dosage across an array of extracurricular activities – for example, school-level differences in the implementation of a district-wide program to promote extracurricular participation – are easier to imagine in theory than to identify in practice.

If it proves infeasible to implement more rigorous causal methods, future studies should at least include a robust set of covariates, measured prior to extracurricular participation, that

account for individual differences in motivation, personality, educational values, and relevant family variables such as parents' involvement in their children's education. Constructs within these domains undoubtedly have implications for both selection into extracurricular activities and college graduation. Additionally, to the already extensive list of demographic covariates used in the present study, future work should include a control for household income, given its links to both extracurricular participation (Feldman & Matjasko, 2005) and college graduation (Bailey & Dynarski, 2011). Although we used two closely related covariates – parent education and attendance at a Title I high school – a measure of household income was not available to us.

Future studies may also consider whether comparable associations between our extracurricular measures and college graduation exist when school- and community-sponsored activities are considered separately. Data differentiating activities by sponsorship were not available in the Common App. Although research generally suggests that both school- and community-sponsored activities predict positive academic outcomes (Feldman & Matjasko, 2005; Farb & Matjasko, 2012), differences in academic outcomes as a function of sponsorship have been noted (Brown & Evans, 2002; Chambers & Schreiber, 2004; Marsh & Kleitman, 2002). The direction of these differences varies, however, and not all evidence supports the rather intuitive notion that school-sponsored activities, when compared to community-sponsored activities, should be more strongly linked to academic outcomes. Indeed, one study actually found that participation in community-sponsored activities was a better predictor of students' connection to school than was participation in school-sponsored activities (Brown & Evans, 2002). Thus, the likely direction of any differences in college graduation rates as a function of extracurricular sponsorship remains unclear.

It would also be prudent to attempt to replicate our findings using nationally

representative data. Despite the large sample size, our findings generalize only to students in the Common App population, which is composed of more selective institutions (e.g., community colleges are not included; www.commonapp.org). Further, because students may perceive a benefit to reporting many extracurricular activities on college applications, our measures of extracurricular involvement may reflect motivations, biases, and perceptions that we can neither assess nor control for. For example, evidence that students who participate in a moderate, versus high, number of activities are more likely to graduate within four (versus six) years may not, in fact, be attributed to differences in extracurricular influences at all, but to differences in students' understanding of college admissions priorities. Students with a better understanding of admissions, who may also be better positioned to graduate on time (Engle, 2007), may understand that colleges are looking for well-rounded students with strong commitments to their interests and report only a moderate number of activities in which they are very engaged.

Despite these limitations, our findings provide a solid foundation for future research on the associations between extracurricular dosage in high school, college extracurricular participation, and the timing of college graduation. Using alternate causal methods with representative data, future studies should attempt to replicate the positive associations that emerged here between extracurricular dosage and the attainment of a bachelor's degree, as well as the association between high levels of extracurricular involvement and longer paths to a degree. Investigators should also test explanatory mechanisms and explore the long-term implications of different delayed paths to a four-year degree. A longer path to graduation may not necessarily be disadvantageous. If such a path reflects strategic planning designed to maximize performance in the academic and extracurricular arenas over a longer period of time, any short-term costs may be outweighed by long-term gains in human and social capital.

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Footnotes

¹ Tests of simple slopes are often used to unpack interactions between independent variables and moderators. When neither the independent variable nor moderator have curvilinear relationships with the outcome, the definition of a simple slope is straightforward – it is the effect of the independent variable at a specified value of the moderator. All interactions identified in the present study, however, included at least one quadratic term. When the relationship between an independent variable, X , and an outcome, Y , is curvilinear, the slope of the curve changes as X changes. Thus, when a variable, Z , moderates a curvilinear relationship between X and Y , the simple slope is computed as the effect of X at specified values of both Z and X (see Aiken & West, 1991, p. 62-99). That is, separate simple slopes must be computed for each pair of X and Z values. Because this can make interpretation difficult, Aiken and West have (1991) outlined procedures for computing a “linear coefficient” (summarizing the linear effect of X on Y) and a “quadratic coefficient” (summarizing the quadratic effect of X on Y) at each level of the moderator. We use this terminology and follow these procedures. We also test the statistical significance of these coefficients using formulas provided by Aiken and West (1991).

² Scholars have for decades debated the proper default p -level for a significant null hypothesis test. The consensus seems to be moving in a more conservative direction. In a recent and prominent paper, Benjamin et al. (2017) argued for a change from $p < .05$ to $p < .005$. Others have urged this change as well (Greenwald, Gonzales, Harris, & Guthrie, 1996; Johnson, 2013). To maintain consistency with our other work on this dataset, we have adopted $p < .01$ as our official criterion for statistical significance. However, with two exceptions (the coefficients for the Latino [$p = .009$] and homeschool [$p = .007$] control variables in Table 2, Models 2 and 3, respectively), we note that all p values in this study denoted $p < .01$ were, in fact, less than .005.

Table 1
Descriptive statistics for all variables

	M(SD)	%
On-time bachelor's attainment	--	42%
Late bachelor's attainment	--	35%
No bachelor's attainment	--	22%
Number of activities	5.14(1.99)	--
Duration	2.52(0.77)	--
Proportion sports	0.27(0.29)	--
Female	--	55%
No parents with degree	--	26%
One parent with degree	--	24%
Two parents with degree	--	49%
Married parents	--	78%
English as first language	--	88%
White	--	51%
African American	--	6%
Latino	--	6%
Asian	--	10%
Other race/ethnicity	--	8%
No race reported	--	18%
Test composite	1824.9(268.8)	--
Non-Title I public school	--	51%
Title I public school	--	16%
Private school	--	33%
Homeschool	--	>1%
Institutional graduation rate	0.58(0.22)	--

Note. Data are unimputed.

Table 2

Regression models: Effects of high school extracurriculars on college outcomes and planned college activities

Predictors	Model 1:	Model 2:	Model 3:	Model 4:
	On-time bachelor's (vs. no bachelor's)	Late bachelor's (vs. no bachelor's)	On-time bachelor's (vs. late bachelor's)	Number of planned college activities
	OR(99% CI)	OR(99% CI)	OR(99% CI)	B(99% CI)
Number of activities	1.07(1.06-1.08)***	1.11(1.10-1.12)***	0.97(0.96-0.97)***	0.19(0.19 - 0.19)***
Number of activities sq	0.99(0.98-0.99)***	--	0.99(0.98-0.99)***	-0.01(-0.01 - -0.00)***
Duration	1.11(1.09-1.14)***	1.16(1.14-1.19)***	0.94(0.92-0.96)***	0.18(0.17 - 0.19)***
Duration sq	--	0.91(0.89-0.94)***	--	0.09(0.08 - 0.10)***
Number x duration	1.00(0.99-1.02)	1.02(1.01-1.03)***	0.98(0.97-0.99)***	0.00(-0.00 - 0.00)
Number x duration sq	--	0.98(0.97-0.99)***	--	-0.00(-0.00 - 0.00)
Number sq x duration	1.00(0.99-1.00)**	--	1.00(0.99-1.00)**	0.00(0.00 - 0.00)***
Number sq x duration sq	--	--	--	-0.01(-0.02 - -0.01)***
Proportion sports	1.09(1.04-1.15)***	1.15(1.10-1.21)***	0.95(0.91-0.99)**	-0.49(-0.51 - -0.48)***
Female	1.62(1.57-1.67)***	1.32(1.28-1.35)***	1.18(1.15-1.20)***	-0.04(-0.05 - -0.04)***
One parent with degree	1.21(1.16-1.25)***	1.19(1.15-1.24)***	1.02(0.99-1.05)	-0.00(-0.01 - 0.01)
Two parents with degree	1.22(1.18-1.27)***	1.33(1.29-1.38)***	0.91(0.88-0.94)***	0.01(0.00 - 0.02)***
Married parents	1.36(1.32-1.40)***	1.25(1.21-1.29)***	1.06(1.03-1.09)***	-0.04(-0.05 - -0.04)***
English as first language	1.39(1.32-1.45)***	1.48(1.42-1.56)***	0.93(0.89-0.96)***	-0.17(-0.18 - -0.16)***
African American	0.66(0.62-0.70)***	0.91(0.86-0.96)***	0.70(0.66-0.74)***	0.16(0.15 - 0.17)***
Latino	0.78(0.73-0.83)***	1.06(1.00-1.12)**	0.73(0.70-0.77)***	0.02(0.01 - 0.04)***
Asian	0.68(0.65-0.72)***	0.79(0.75-0.83)***	0.89(0.85-0.92)***	0.14(0.13 - 0.16)***
Other race/ethnicity	0.70(0.67-0.74)***	0.84(0.80-0.88)***	0.85(0.82-0.89)***	0.10(0.09 - 0.11)***
No race reported	0.84(0.81-0.87)***	0.80(0.78-0.84)***	1.05(1.02-1.09)***	0.05(0.04 - 0.06)***
Test composite	1.23(1.21-1.26)***	1.22(1.19-1.24)***	0.95(0.94-0.97)***	-0.01(-0.02 - -0.00)***
Title I public school	0.82(0.79-0.86)***	0.92(0.89-0.96)***	0.91(0.88-0.94)***	-0.01(-0.02 - 0.00)
Private school	0.72(0.69-0.74)***	0.71(0.69-0.73)***	1.03(1.00-1.06)**	0.10(0.09 - 0.10)***
Homeschool	0.41(0.32-0.52)***	0.51(0.41-0.66)***	0.78(0.61-0.99)**	-0.00(-0.07 - 0.06)
Institutional graduation rate	2.22(2.18-2.26)***	1.48(1.46-1.51)***	1.45(1.43-1.47)***	0.04(0.04 - 0.04)***
N	201,125	179,713	241,778	311,308

Note. Data are multiply imputed (m=25). Activity variables were mean centered. All other continuous variables were z-score standardized. sq = squared. -- = predictor dropped due to non-significance. OR = odds ratio = (odds that outcome=1)/(odds that outcome = 0). B = unstandardized coefficient; interpreted as the increase in the outcome associated with a one unit increase in the predictor.

** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Table 3

Linear and quadratic coefficients for the effect of number of activities on graduation outcomes, as a function of duration

Duration level	On-time bachelor's (versus no bachelor's)		Late bachelor's (versus no bachelor's)	On-time bachelor's (versus late bachelor's)	
	Linear slope	Quadratic slope	Linear slope	Linear slope	Quadratic slope
	OR(99%CI)	OR(99%CI)	OR(99%CI)	OR(99%CI)	OR(99%CI)
1 year	1.06(1.04-1.08) ^{***}	0.99(0.99-1.00)	1.02(1.01-1.04) ^{***}	1.00(0.99-1.02)	0.99(0.99-1.00) ^{***}
2 years	1.06(1.05-1.08) ^{***}	0.99(0.99-0.99) ^{***}	1.09(1.08-1.10) ^{***}	0.98(0.97-0.99) ^{***}	0.99(0.99-0.99) ^{***}
3 years	1.07(1.06-1.08) ^{***}	0.99(0.98-0.99) ^{***}	1.11(1.10-1.12) ^{***}	0.95(0.95-0.96) ^{***}	0.99(0.98-0.99) ^{***}
4 years	1.07(1.05-1.10) ^{***}	0.98(0.97-0.99) ^{***}	1.10(1.07-1.12) ^{***}	0.93(0.92-0.95) ^{***}	0.98(0.98-0.99) ^{***}
<i>N</i>	201,125		179,713	241,778	

Note. This table provides results from follow-up tests that unpack the interactions between number of activities and activity duration in Models 1-3 in Table 2. Coefficients and covariance/variance terms from Models 1-3 in Table 2 were used to compute these values and corresponding significance tests, following procedures outlined by Aiken and West (1991). The first two columns of results present the linear and quadratic coefficients (ORs) for number of activities at each level of activity duration in the model predicting on-time bachelor's (versus no bachelor's; Table 2, Model 1). The third column of results presents the linear coefficient (OR) for number of activities at each level of duration in the model predicting late bachelor's (versus no bachelor's; Table 2, Model 2). The quadratic term for number of activities in this model was not significant and was therefore excluded from the model. Finally, the fourth and fifth columns of results present the linear and quadratic coefficients (ORs) for number of activities at each level of activity duration in the model predicting on-time bachelor's (versus late bachelor's; Table 2, Model 3).

^{***} $p < .001$

Table 4

Linear and quadratic coefficients for the effect of number of activities on planned college activities, as a function of duration

Duration level	Linear slope	Quadratic slope
	B(99%CI)	B(99%CI)
1 year	0.19(0.18-0.19)***	-0.04(-0.05 - -0.04)***
2 years	0.19(0.19-0.19)***	-0.01(-0.01 - -0.01)***
3 years	0.19(0.19-0.19)***	-0.01(-0.01 - -0.01)***
4 years	0.19(0.18-0.20)***	-0.03(-0.04 - -0.03)***
<i>N</i>	311,308	

Note. This table provides results from follow-up tests that unpack the interaction between number of high school activities and activity duration in the model predicting number of planned college activities (Table 2, Model 4). Coefficients and covariance/variance terms from Table 2, Model 4 were used to compute these values and corresponding significance tests, following procedures outlined by Aiken and West (1991). The first column of results presents the linear coefficients for number of high school activities at each level of activity duration. The second column of results presents the quadratic coefficients for number of high school activities at each level of duration.

*** $p < .001$

Table 5

Regression models: Effects of number of planned college activities on college outcomes

Predictors	Model 1:	Model 2:	Model 3:
	On-time bachelor's (vs. no bachelor's)	Late bachelor's (vs. no bachelor's)	On-time bachelor's (vs. late bachelor's)
	OR(99% CI)	OR(99% CI)	OR(99% CI)
Number of planned college activities	0.99(0.98-1.00)**	1.01(1.00-1.02)***	0.97(0.96-0.98)***
Number of planned college activities sq	--	--	1.00(1.00-1.01)**
Proportion sports	0.98(0.93-1.03)	1.05(1.00-1.11)**	0.93(0.89-0.97)***
Female	1.68(1.63-1.73)***	1.37(1.33-1.41)***	1.16(1.14-1.19)***
One parent with degree	1.25(1.20-1.29)***	1.23(1.19-1.28)***	1.02(0.98-1.05)
Two parents with degree	1.29(1.24-1.33)***	1.41(1.36-1.46)***	0.90(0.87-0.93)***
Married parents	1.40(1.35-1.44)***	1.30(1.26-1.34)***	1.05(1.02-1.08)***
English as first language	1.41(1.35-1.48)***	1.52(1.45-1.60)***	0.91(0.87-0.95)***
African American	0.65(0.61-0.68)***	0.89(0.84-0.94)***	0.71(0.67-0.75)***
Latino	0.77(0.73-0.82)***	1.04(0.98-1.10)	0.74(0.71-0.78)***
Asian	0.67(0.64-0.71)***	0.77(0.73-0.81)***	0.90(0.86-0.94)***
Other race/ethnicity	0.70(0.66-0.74)***	0.83(0.79-0.87)***	0.86(0.82-0.90)***
No race reported	0.82(0.79-0.85)***	0.78(0.75-0.81)***	1.06(1.03-1.09)***
Test composite	1.29(1.27-1.31)***	1.28(1.26-1.30)***	0.95(0.93-0.96)***
Title I public school	0.83(0.80-0.87)***	0.93(0.90-0.97)***	0.90(0.88-0.93)***
Private school	0.72(0.70-0.75)***	0.71(0.69-0.73)***	1.04(1.01-1.07)***
Homeschool	0.39(0.30-0.50)***	0.49(0.39-0.63)***	0.78(0.61-0.99)***
Institutional graduation rate	2.27(2.23-2.32)***	1.52(1.49-1.55)***	1.45(1.43-1.47)***
<i>N</i>	201,125	179,713	241,778

Note. Data are multiply imputed ($m=25$). Activity variables were mean centered. All other continuous variables were z-score standardized. sq = squared. -- = predictor dropped due to non-significance.

** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Figure 1. Significant interactions between number of high school activities and duration in models predicting college outcomes. Error bars on each line reflect 99% prediction intervals.

Figure 2. Significant interaction between number of high school activities squared and duration squared in models predicting number of planned college activities. Error bars on each line reflect 99% prediction intervals.

Figure 3. Association between number of planned activities during college and the probability of on-time (versus late) bachelor's degree attainment. Error bars on each line reflect 99% prediction intervals.